

Supplemental information to Ruperti et al. (2023): Molecular profiling of sponge deflation reveals an ancient relaxant-inflammatory response

Naming convention of the sponge “movement”

The specific “movement” of sponges discussed in Ruperti, *et al.* (2023) has fascinated humans throughout millennia, dating back to descriptions of **Aristotle** in his *History of Animals*, written around **350 B.C.** There, Aristotle notes that sponges are known to sense their surroundings and as evidence (“σημείον”) he provides the fact that the sponge “collects himself” (“συνάγει εαυτόν”) when disturbed, indicating an inward movement (“συνάγει”) by the organism itself (“εαυτόν”), i.e. as a clear intrinsic behavior, as opposed to something facilitated by external forces. A sponge “collects himself if it perceives any purpose of tearing it up, and renders the task more difficult. The sponge does the same thing when the winds and waves are violent [...]”. Interestingly, even then, this movement appeared to be debated, as “there are some persons who dispute this, as the natives of Torona”. Almost identical to Aristotle, **Plinius the Elder** (*The Natural History*, **77 B.C.**) describes how sponges “contract” when strong waves are hitting them (“Intellectum inesse iis apparet, quia, ubi avulsorem sensere, *contractae* multo difficilius abstrahuntur; hoc idem fluctu pulsante faciunt.”). The term “contraction” (from Latin “con-” meaning “together” and “trahere” meaning “to pull”) has survived the centuries and can be found in **Ellis and Knight (1765)** (Ellis 1765), describing the contraction of “fecal orifices” (ostia) on the surface of the sponge. For this, they use the pairs “contraction” and “dilation” as well as “systole” and “diastole”. In 1825 **Grant** (Grant 1825) observed the movement and noted that sponges “vomiting forth, from a circular cavity, an impetuous torrent of liquid matter”. With this observation, he concluded that “sponges must be animals and not, as Aristotle believed, vegetables” (Meech 2008). In the 19th and 20th century many authors described their observations using the antonyms “contraction” and “relaxation” (**Lieberkühn (1859)** (Lieberkühn, n.d.): “Contractionszustant”, **McNair (1923)** (McNAIR 1923): “Contraction/Constriction” vs “Relaxation” in *Ephydatia muelleri*, **Pavans de Ceccatty (1960)** (De Ceccatty, Cargouil, and Corabœuf n.d.): “Contraction” in *Tethya lyncurium*, **Prosser (1962)** (Prosser, Nagai, and Nystrom 1962): “Contraction” vs “Relaxation” in multiple marine and freshwater species, **Emson (1966)** (Emson 1966): “Contraction” vs “Relaxation in *Cliona celata*, **De Vos, Van de Vyver (1981)** (de Vos and Van de Vyver 1981): “Contraction spontanée” in *E. fluviatilis*). **Parker (1910)** (Parker 1910) used slightly different descriptions for the different states such as “shriveled, rugose” vs. “filled out” or “contraction” vs “expansion” when he worked on *Stylotella heliophila*. In the late 20th century, **Weissenfels (1984, 1990)** worked extensively on freshwater sponges such as *E. muelleri* and *S. lacustris*. Whereas in earlier publications, he describes his observations as “endogene Kontraktionsrhythmik” (“endogenous contraction rhythm”) (Weissenfels 1984), at later stages he uses the term “condensation rhythm” (Latin “con-” meaning “together”, “densus” meaning “dense”) to potentially avoid the implication of active processes. He states that the condensation of the mesohyl “giv[es] the impression of a contraction” and that “rhythmic changes that at first glance appear to be contractions [...]. [A]ctually however, the process is a condensation initiated by [...] a rapid swelling of all mesenchymal cells”. In later years, **Nickel (2006, 2007, 2011)**, **Leys (2007, 2010)** and **Nichols (2021)** used different descriptors for different phases of the behavior. In general, **Nickel** used the terms “contraction” vs. “expansion” in *Tethya wilhelma* (Ellwanger and Nickel 2006) (Ellwanger, Eich, and Nickel 2007). In the expanded state, all canal systems are “inflated” (Nickel et al.

2011). **Leys** introduced the term “inflation-contraction” response in *E. muelleri* (Elliott and Leys 2007, 2010) “Inflation” suddenly described the “contraction” of McNair, De Vos and Weissenfels in which the excurrent canal system of freshwater sponges is expanding and the top view gives the impression of an “inflation”. In contrast, “contraction” describes the return into the default state. At the same time, this return is called “relaxation”. Most recently, **Nichols** returned to “contraction cycle” describing the whole-body volume reduction in *E. muelleri*.

This list gives an account of the complication regarding the consistent and precise terminology of the observation of sponge movement. Ruperti *et al.* devised a straightforward naming convention, taking the history of this field into account and combining it with new insights from their study. For this, they recognized the importance of separating different levels of organization: (1) organismal (whole-body) changes, (2) canal changes and (3) cellular changes. On an organismal level (1), they decided for a terminology agnostic to the cellular processes and would therefore abstain from the usage of “contraction” as it suggests an active process, commonly through actomyosin activity. They decided to use the term “deflation” to describe the process in which the sponge is reducing its body volume, irrespective of the individual tissue changes. In contrast, they call the expansion of body volume “inflation”. As noted by Weissenfels, Leys, Nickel and Nichols, incurrent canal systems together with the epithelial tent and the excurrent canal system behave antagonistically (2). During deflation, the incurrent canal system and the tent are “collapsing” (also (Colgren and Nichols 2022)) while the excurrent system is “expanding”. Only on the level of individual cells (3), such as pinacocytes, they decided to utilize “contraction” vs. “relaxation” because it directly relates to the cellular process of actomyosin contraction vs. relaxation. Since contraction equals increased tension in actomyosin stress fibers, they also use the phrase “tension increase” for contraction and opposing “tension decrease” for relaxation. Notably, actomyosin contraction can be isometric, i.e. involving tension increase without length changes, which is assumed in Ruperti *et al.* for the epithelial tent during re-establishment of the inflated default state.

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